

ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT MOTIVATION OF ADOLESCENTS IN RELATION TO THEIR ANXIETY LEVEL

Dr. Sarvjeet Kaur Brar

Assistant Professor, G.H.G Harparkash College of Education for Women, Sidhwan
Khurd, Ludhiana, Punjab

Cite This Article: Dr. Sarvjeet Kaur Brar, "Academic Achievement Motivation of Adolescents in Relation to their Anxiety Level", International Journal of Applied and Advanced Scientific Research, Volume 3, Issue 1, Page Number 96-99, 2018.

Abstract:

The present study was undertaken to investigate the relationship of Academic achievement motivation of adolescents in relation to their Anxiety level. The study was confined to 200 adolescent students studying in different schools of Ludhiana district of Panjab, India. Male and female Students within the age range of 16-17 years were selected from urban and rural areas by using stratified random sampling technique. Two valid and reliable tools The Academic Achievement Motivation Test prepared by Dr. T.R.Sharma(1971) and Academic Anxiety Scale developed by A.K. Singh and A. Sengupta(1984) were used. The obtained data were analyzed by mean, SD, t-test and Product Moment co-efficient of correlation. The findings of the study revealed significant difference in Academic achievement motivation and anxiety level with respect to gender but no significant difference was found in relation to locale variation. Another finding of the study was the significant negative relationship between Academic achievement motivation and anxiety level of adolescents.

Key Words: Academic Achievement Motivation, Anxiety Level & Adolescents

Introduction:

In the present competitive world everyone desires for a high level of achievement. Achievement Motivation is a consistent striving force by which an individual achieve success to attain standard of excellence. In this modern competitive age achievement is considered to be a key factor for educational, personal and social progress of an individual. Motivation is one of the major concerns of teachers in the classroom and is the essential part of learning. By persuasion of affection, care, threat, reward and other actions and effects, motivation can be inculcated by the teacher. Causing fewer disciplinary problems. Motivating the student to learn to the best of their capacities is one of the basic requirement of classroom teachings. It is the motivation that provides force and direction to the behavior of students. Academic achievement motivation and study habits have been found as important components of education (Haertelet, al. 1981). There are number of factors which effect the academic achievement of students during their studies. These factors may be individual, home and school environment related factors like- self-concept, self- confidence, motivation, interest and anxiety etc. Anxiety is one of the most important factors that can affect an individual during studies. Examination stress and test anxiety are pervasive problems among students. Every year, millions of students underperform in school and university because of heightened stress and anxiety, which is set of phenomenological, physiological and behavioral responses that results negative consequences or failure in an exam or similar evaluative situation (Zeidner, 1998). Anxiety is now seen as possible factor that affects a person's academic achievement. It varies markedly from one student to another. Thus, some individuals will be relatively calm when it comes to completing a test, while others will generally perceive examinations as more dangerous or threatening and experience more intense levels of stress and state anxiety (Spielberger & Vagg, 1995).

Rationale of the Study:

Academic achievement motivation plays an important role to achieve educational goals of the students. Keeping in the mind, the recent developments in educational field, there is a great need of Academic achievement motivation for being successful. Motivated students become secretly confident and can easily face the challenges of dynamic world of education. There is great need of Academic achievement motivation for students, because motivation effects the academic achievement of the students. The present study is about the academic achievement motivation of the students. Academic motivation is the attitudes towards school learning and enthusiasm for academic achievement. Academic achievement motivation involves measuring items such as work habits and scholastic expectation of learners. Present study will help in understanding the role of Academic achievement motivation for good academic performance. This will help parents, teachers and guidance worker to understand the students and have necessary action related to promoting and encouraging Academic achievement motivation from an early age for good academic results.

The development of early academic achievement motivation has significant implications for later academic years. A great deal of researches has found that students with high Academic achievement motivation are more likely to have increased levels of academic performance and have lower dropout rates. So, the investigator feels that raising of the academic achievement motivation of the students may go a long way in enhancing their academic results. That is why; the present study endeavored to examine the achievement motivation of adolescent students and its relationship with their anxiety level.

Statement of the Problem:

The problem under study is formally entitled as “Academic achievement motivation of adolescents in relation to their anxiety level”

Methodology:

Design of the Study:

The method employed in the present study was descriptive survey method. The study was conducted on adolescent students of secondary and higher secondary schools of Ludhiana district of Punjab State of India.

Tools Used:

The Academic Achievement Motivation Test prepared by Dr. T.R. Sharma (1971) and Academic Anxiety Scale developed by A.K. Singh and A. Sengupta (1984) was used for the purpose of data collection by the researcher.

Statistical Techniques Used:

Descriptive statistics like, means, standard deviation, coefficient of correlation and Critical Ratio were calculated to analyze the data in this study.

Sample:

According to the objectives of this study, the population of this research was adolescent students of secondary and higher secondary school of the Ludhiana district of Panjab (India). In this research sample was selected randomly from secondary and high schools situated in rural and urban areas in the Panjab district. Researcher selected a sample of 200 adolescents (100 boys and 100 girls) from different schools.

Objectives:

The objectives of the study were-

- ✓ To compare the Academic achievement motivation of male and female adolescent students.
- ✓ To compare the Academic achievement motivation of rural and urban adolescent students.
- ✓ To compare the Anxiety levels of male and female adolescent students.
- ✓ To compare the Anxiety levels of rural and urban adolescent students.
- ✓ To study the relationship between Academic achievement motivations and Anxiety levels of the adolescent students.

Hypotheses:

- ✓ There is no significant difference in the Academic achievement motivation of male and female adolescent students.
- ✓ There is no significant difference in the Academic achievement motivation of rural and urban adolescent students.
- ✓ There is no significant difference in the Anxiety levels of male and female adolescent students.
- ✓ There is no significant difference in the Anxiety levels of rural and urban adolescent students.
- ✓ There is no significant relationship between the Academic achievement motivation and Anxiety levels of adolescent students.

Analysis and Interpretation:

Comparison of the Academic Achievement Motivation of Male and Female Adolescents:

To compare the Academic achievement motivation of male and female adolescents the researcher formulated the hypothesis as “there is no significant difference in the Academic achievement motivation of male and female adolescent students” and tested the hypothesis.

Table 1: Significance of difference in the Academic achievement motivation of male and female adolescents

Group	N	Mean	S.D	C.R Value	Inference
Male adolescents	100	27.61	5.69	2.30	Significant at 0.05 level
Female adolescents	100	29.24	4.21		

Table 1 show that, The C. R. value is 2.30 which is significant at 0.05 level of confidence. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected and it is concluded that there is significant difference in the Academic achievement motivation of the male and female adolescent students.

Comparison of the Academic Achievement Motivation of Rural and Urban Adolescent Student:

To compare the Academic achievement motivation of rural and urban adolescents the researcher formulated the hypothesis as “there is no significant difference in the Academic achievement motivation of rural and urban adolescent students” and tested the hypothesis.

Table 2: Significance of difference in the Academic achievement motivation of students of rural and urban areas

Group	N	Mean	S.D	C.R value	Inference
Rural adolescents	100	27.94	5.17	1.36	Not Significant
Urban adolescents	100	28.91	4.93		

Table 2 shows that, The C.R value is 1.36 which is not significant at 0.05 level of confidence. Thus, the null hypothesis is accepted and it is concluded that there is no significant difference in the Academic achievement motivation of rural and urban adolescent students.

Comparison of the Anxiety Level of Male and Female Adolescent Students:

To compare the Anxiety level of male and female adolescents the researchers formulated the hypothesis as “there is no significant difference in the Anxiety level of male and female adolescent students” and tested the hypothesis.

Table 3: Significance of difference in the Anxiety level of male and female adolescent students

Group	N	Mean	S.D	C.R value	Inference
Male adolescents	100	12.41	2.40	2.32	Significant at 0.05 level.
Female adolescents	100	13.11	1.82		

Table 3 shows that, The C.R. value is 2.32 which is significant at 0.05 level of confidence. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected and it is concluded that there is significant difference in the Anxiety level of male and female adolescent students.

Comparison of the Anxiety Level of Rural and Urban Adolescent Students:

To compare the Spiritual Intelligence of rural and urban adolescents the researcher formulated the hypothesis as “there is no significant difference in the Anxiety level of rural and urban adolescent students” and tested the hypothesis.

Table 4: Significance of difference in the Anxiety level of rural and urban adolescent students

Group	N	Mean	S.D	C.R Value	Inference
Rural adolescents	100	12.46	2.35	1.22	Not Significant
Urban adolescents	100	12.85	2.16		

Table 4 shows that, The C.R. value is 1.22 which is not significant. Thus, the null hypothesis is accepted and it is concluded that there is no significant difference in the Anxiety level of rural and urban adolescent students.

Relationship between the Academic Achievement Motivation and Anxiety Level of the Adolescent Students:

To study the relationship between the Academic achievement motivation and Anxiety level of the adolescent students the researcher formulated the hypothesis as “There is no significant relationship between the Academic achievement motivation and Anxiety level of adolescent students” and tested the hypothesis.

Table 5: Coefficient of correlation between the Academic achievement motivation and Anxiety level of the adolescent students

Variable	N	Coefficient of Correlation	Inference
Academic achievement motivation	200	-0.22	Significant at .01 level
Anxiety level	200		

Table 5 shows that, the value of correlation between the of the Academic achievement motivation and Anxiety level of adolescent students is -0.22. The value is significant at 0.01 level of confidence so, the null hypothesis that “There is no significant relationship between the Academic achievement motivation and Anxiety level of the adolescent students” is rejected and it can be inferred that there is significant negative relationship between the Academic achievement motivation and Anxiety level of the adolescent students.

Findings and Discussion:

The purpose of the current study was to examine any significant differences in Academic achievement motivation and anxiety level of adolescent students. In this research the obtained data was tabulated and analyzed. ‘t’ test was employed to study the significance of difference between the means of score of Academic achievement motivation and Anxiety level with respect to gender (boys and girls) and locale (urban and rural). Pearson’s correlation method was employed to examine the relationship between academic achievement motivation and anxiety level of adolescents. Result revealed the following findings:

- ✓ There was significant difference in the Academic achievement motivation of the male and female adolescent students.
- ✓ There was no significant difference in the Academic achievement motivation of rural and urban adolescent students.
- ✓ There was no significant difference in the Anxiety level of male and female adolescent students.
- ✓ There was no significant difference in the Anxiety level of rural and urban adolescent students.
- ✓ Academic achievement motivation and Anxiety level of adolescents were significantly and negatively related with each other.

Results are in line with earlier studies conducted by Adsul and Kamble (2008) and Chaturvedi (2009) who investigated the significant difference in achievement motivation possessed by college students with respect to gender, economic background and caste difference but no statistically significant difference was found between the rural and urban subsamples on academic achievement motivation. The result was not in conformity with study conducted by Mohanty (2007) who revealed significant differences in the academic achievement of rural and urban students.

Conclusion and Recommendations:

The findings of the present study showed that there was significant negative correlation between the academic achievement motivation and anxiety level among adolescent students. It means high anxiety level

group have low academic achievement motivation and low anxiety level group have high academic achievement motivation.

Achievement motivation is greatly influenced by the parental behavior. Therefore, parents should be affectionate enough and should listen and understand all the problems and needs of their children and should try to solve them. They should encourage the children to meet each and every problem of their life by participating in different life situations with courage and being flexible.

It is imperative both for parents and educators to understand, promote and encourage achievement motivation from an early age. Teachers and the parents should set high goals before the students so that they should try to achieve them and they should develop the tendency of high Academic achievement motivation. Teachers at all levels should implement strategies to enhance the achievement motivation of students by developing a positive classroom climate and reducing the anxiety levels of the students. It is joint responsibility of parents, teachers and guidance workers to motivate children towards their academic achievements and try to remove the de-motivating anxiety leading factors from the environment of the students.

References:

1. Adsul, R. K. and Kamble, V. (2008). Achievement motivation as a Function of Gender, Economic Background and Caste Differences in College Students. *Journal of the Indian Academy of Applied Psychology*, Volume 34, No.2, Pp 323-327.
2. Chaturvedi, M. (2009). School Environment, Achievement Motivation and Achievement motivation *Indian Journal of Social Science Research*. Vol.6, No. 2, Pp. 29- 37.
3. Haertel, G. D., Walberg, H.J. and Haertel, E.H. (1981). Socio-psychological Environments and Learning: A Quantitative Synthesis. *British Journal of Educational Research*, 7, pp. 27– 36.
4. Mohanty, P. (1999). Comparative role of self-concept, achievement motivation and test anxiety as predictors to academic achievement. Unpublished Ph.D. Dissertation in Education, Utkal University.
5. Sharma, T. R. (1971) *Manual for Academic Achievement Motivation Test*. Agra; National Psychological Corporation.
6. Singh, A. K. and Sengupta, A. (1984) *Manual for Academic Anxiety Scale*. Agra; National Psychological Corporation.
7. Spielberger, C. D. & Vagg, P. R. (1995). Test anxiety: A transactional process. In C. D.
8. Spielberger & P. Vagg (Eds.), *Test anxiety: theory, assessment, and treatment* (pp. 3-14). Washington, DC: Taylor & Francis.
9. Zeidner, M. (1998). *Test anxiety: The state of the art*. New York: Plenum.